

OVERVIEW OF MOTHERS' KNOWLEDGE ABOUT STUNTING IN TODDLERS IN TIKONU VILLAGE, KOLAKA DISTRICT

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Abstract

Background: Stunting is a condition of failure of growth and development of children under five years of age due to stunting according to the ministry of health is a toddler with a z-SD value (Severely stunted) (TNP2K, 2017). The results of the preliminary study of the number of toddlers at the Wundulako health centre were 372. Tikonu Village contributed 22 toddlers who experienced stunting in 2021 (health profile of Kolaka Regency in 2021). **Objective:** This study aims to determine the description of mothers' knowledge about stunting in toddlers in Tikonu village, Wundulako sub-district. **Method:** Using a descriptive research design, the sampling technique used was total sampling, the sample taken from this study was 31 mothers. **Results:** The results of this study found that respondents had poor knowledge (58.06%), sufficient (16.12%), and good (25.80%). **Conclusion:** Based on the results of the study, the majority of respondents had a lack of knowledge, namely (58.06%) So health workers, especially nutritionists, are advised to further improve the quality of counselling and services so that they can reduce the number of children under five years old. Stunting.

Keywords: Maternal Knowledge, Age, Occupation, Stunting, Toddlers.

INTRODUCTION

Stunting is a condition of failure to thrive in infants under five years old due to chronic malnutrition so that children are too short for their age. Malnutrition occurs since the baby is in the womb and in the early period after the baby is born, but the stunting condition is only seen after the baby is 2 years old in Indonesia. Based on data from the *Asian development Bank*, in 2022 the percentage of *Prevalance Of Stunting Among Children Under 5 Years Of Age* in Indonesia was 31.8%, causing Indonesia to rank 10th in the Southeast Asia region. Furthermore, in 2022, based on data from the ministry of health, Indonesia's stunting rate managed to dropped to 21.6% (Ratih 2022).

Given the importance of the problem at the opening of the national working meeting of the family planning development programme, and the reduction of stunting at the bkbn auditorium, the impact of stunting is not only height, but the most dangerous is the low ability of children, when the emergence of chronic diseases that easily enter the child's body. Therefore, it is hoped that the target percentage of *stunting* in Indonesia in 2023 can fall to 14% (Mashudi and Muftiana 2023a).

The prevalence of stunting toddlers has increased from 2020, then in 2022 it decreased by 21.6% and increased again by 29.6% in 2023. The results of the Ministry of Health data research in the Southeast Asia region show that the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia is 30.8%, which shows a decrease from the previous year in 2022 (Bahrun and Wildan 2022).

Based on the results of the nutrition status survey in Indonesia (SSGI) in 2022, the national stunting prevalence is still 21.6%, Southeast Sulawesi province is 27% while Kolaka Regency shows a positive trend every year where when compared to 2019 of 36.2 percent we have reduced by 13.6 percent (Permana, Indrawan. Firlianty, Mentari 2022).

The adverse effects that can be caused by nutritional problems in the short-term period are impaired brain development, intelligence, impaired physical growth and metabolic disorders, while in the long term are decreased cognitive abilities and learning presentation, decreased immunity so that they get sick easily (Migang and Manuntung 2021).

Maternal knowledge about nutrition is one of the factors that can affect food consumption and nutritional status in toddlers. Mothers with sufficient nutritional knowledge will pay attention to the nutritional needs of their children so that they can grow and develop optimally so as to prevent the incidence of stunting in toddlers (Permana, Indrawan. Firlianty, Mentari 2022).

The results of preliminary studies at the Kolaka District Health Office, the number of toddlers in the entire Puskesmas Wundulako is 372 toddlers Of the 9 working areas of the Kolaka District Health Office, Tikonu Village was found to be the working area of UPTD Puskesmas Wundulako with the number of stunted toddlers, namely 22 toddlers in 2023 (Profile of the Puskesmas Wundulako).

Kolaka District Health, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

This research uses descriptive quantitative research. The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative research method because the research wants to describe or describe the facts or circumstances or symptoms that appear. Qualitative descriptive research seeks to describe all existing symptoms or conditions, namely the state of the symptoms according to what they are at the time the research is conducted (Hamzah Muchtar 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on diagram 1 below, it is known that out of a total of 31 respondents, 18 people (58.06%) have poor knowledge, as many as 5 people (16.12%) have sufficient knowledge, as many as 8 people (25.80%) have good knowledge.

Primary Data Source Year 2023

Table 5.2: Frequency Distribution of Knowledge Mothers About Stunting Based on Age in Tikonu Village, Wundulako District, 2023

No.	Age	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	14 - 25 Years	7	22,58
2.	26 - 35 Years	18	58,06
3.	36 - 47 Years	6	19,35
Total		31	100

Primary Data Source Year 2023

Based on Table 5.2 shows that of the 31 respondents aged 14-25 years as many as 7 people (22.58%), aged 26 – 35 years as many as 18 people (58.06%), and aged 36 - 47 years as many as 6 people (19,35%). The majority of respondents aged 26-35 years were 18 people (58,06%).

Based on diagram 2 below shows that of the 31 respondents, 28 were housewives (92.5%), and 3 were mothers with civil servants (7.5%).

Primary Data Source Year 2023

Table 5.4: Frequency Distribution of Mothers' Knowledge about Stunting by age in Tikonu Village, Wundulako Subdistrict, 2023

No	Age	Knowledge						Total (n)	Percentage (%)
		B	aik	Cuk	up	Kur	ang		
		N	%	N	%	N	%		
1.	14-25	2	25	1	20	4	22,22	7	22,58
2.	26-35	4	50	1	20	13	72,22	18	58,06
3.	36-47	2	25	3	60	1	5,55	6	19,35
Total		8	100	5	100	18	100	31	100

Primary Data Source Year 2023

Based on Table 5.4, the author can conclude that maternal knowledge tends to be good in the age range of 14-25 years with the number showing that of the 31 respondents at the age of 14-25 years, 2 mothers with good knowledge (25%), 1 person (20%) with sufficient knowledge, Less knowledgeable 4 people (22.22%).

Respondents with age 26-35 years old mothers with good knowledge were 4 people (50%), respondents with sufficient knowledge were 1 person (20%), respondents with less knowledge were 13 people (72.22%). Age 36-47 years mothers with good knowledge 2 people (25%), respondents with sufficient knowledge were 3 people (60%), respondents with less knowledge were 1 person (5.55%).

Table 5.5: Frequency Distribution of Maternal Knowledge about Stunting by Maternal Occupation in Tikonu Village, Wundulako District, 2023

No.	Jobs	Knowledge						Number (n)	Percentage (%)
		Good		Simply		Less			
		N	%	N	%	N	%		
1.	PNS	3	7,5	0	0	0	0	3	7,5
2.	Employees	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3.	Private	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4.	Farmers	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Self-employed								
5.	IRT	5	11	5	11	18	38	28	92,5
	Total	8	18,5	5	11	18	38	31	100

Primary Data Source Year 2023

Based on Table 5.5 shows that of the 31 maternal respondents who were civil servants as many as 3 people (7.5%), had good knowledge of 3 people (7.5%), respondents with IRT jobs as many people (92.5%) with good knowledge as many as 7 people (20.5%), respondents with sufficient knowledge 10 people (43%) and respondents with poor knowledge as many as 8 people (29%).

DISCUSSION

1. Knowledge

Based on the results of the study, it was found that the level of knowledge was less, namely as many as 14 respondents (29%) and the minority of good knowledge 13 respondents (28%).

This is in line with research (Roza, Wulandini, and Hasanah 2021) on the knowledge of mothers who have *stunting* toddlers at Puskesmas Rejo Sari Kec. Tenayan Raya Pekanbaru 2019 the majority are in the less category, namely 49 people (70.00%). This is supported by research (Permana, Indrawan. Firlianty, Mentari 2022) at the Kedung banteng Health Centre, Banyumasyang Regency which states that there is a relationship between the incidence of *stunting* and maternal knowledge with poor knowledge, which has a risk of increasing 3.27 times the incidence of *stunting* compared to good maternal knowledge.

This is in line with research (Mashudi and Muftiana 2023a) which states that lack of information greatly affects the level of maternal knowledge. (Siswati and Olfah 2020) That *stunting* is a very serious nutritional problem needs to be addressed quickly and appropriately. What is meant by knowing here is that the more often an individual or a person gets

This proves that the majority of respondents lack information about *stunting*.

2. Age

Maternal age has a significant relationship with the incidence of *stunting*. Mothers who are still classified as adolescents (<20 years) when pregnant have a higher risk of having stunted offspring than mothers of reproductive age (20-35 years). This shows that the age of a mother is said to be mature when she is 20 years old and above. However, the knowledge of mothers who are fairly young is very much in the village. This is evident from the research conducted when the respondent fills out the questionnaire.

From the results of research conducted in Tikonu village where 31 respondents at the age of 14-25 years showed that of the 31 respondents at the age of 14-25 years mothers who had good knowledge 2 people (25%), knowledgeable enough 1 person (20%), knowledgeable less 4 people (22.22%). Respondents

Age 26-35 years old mothers with good knowledge as many as 4 people (50%), respondents with sufficient knowledge 1 person (20%), respondents with less knowledge 13 people (72.22%). Age 36-47 years mothers with good knowledge 2 people (25%), respondents with sufficient knowledge as many as 3 people (60%), respondents with less knowledge as many as 1 person (5.55%).

So it can be concluded that age does not affect maternal knowledge, because most respondents are well informed at the age range of 14-25 years. This is in line with the results (Hamzah Muchtar 2021). which states that the age level of breastfeeding mothers with the level of knowledge about *stunting* does not show a relationship between age and level of knowledge.

3. Jobs

Statistically there is no relationship between maternal employment and the incidence of *stunting* in toddlers. The results of research conducted in Tikonu Village can be concluded that maternal employment does not affect knowledge. This is because the mother's job does not guarantee more knowledge related to the problem of *stunting*, because there are 3 respondents of mothers who are civil servants (7.5%), 3 people (7.5%) have good knowledge, respondents with IRT jobs as much as 3 people (7.5%).

44 people (92.5%) with good knowledge as many as 10 people (20.5%), respondents with sufficient knowledge 20 people (43%) and respondents with poor knowledge as many as 14 people (29%). And 10 people (20.5%) with good knowledge are housewives, when viewed from the work of housewives, they will have more time to care for their children compared to working m o t h e r s , so that housewives tend to be more active in participating in posyandu activities and counselling activities about *stunting* so that their knowledge is broad about *stunting*. This is in line with the results (Hamzah Muchtar 2021) which say there is no relationship between maternal work and knowledge in preventing *stunting* in children.

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